

Victim Protection in India: Legal Framework and Judicial Interpretations

Paper Id : 20379 Submission Date : 2025-06-12 Acceptance Date : 2025-06-21 Publication Date : 2025-06-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16321663

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Pardeep Kumar

Bajaj

Research Scholar

Law

Shri Guru Granth Sahib

World University

Fatehgarh Sahib, Haryana,

India

Abstract

The Indian criminal justice system has traditionally focused on the rights of the accused, often sidelining the needs of the victims. However, recent developments have sought to rectify this imbalance, emphasizing victim protection as an essential aspect of justice delivery. Victims are now recognized as integral participants in the legal process, with rights to protection, compensation, and participation.

Keywords Legal Framework, Judicial Interpretations.

Introduction

In India, the judiciary has played a crucial role in interpreting laws in a victim-centric manner, while legislation such as the Code of Criminal Procedure (CrPC), Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act (POCSO), and various state compensation schemes have provided a legal foundation for victims' rights.

Objective of study The primary objective of this research paper is to critically analyze the present legal framework for victim protection in India and assess the role of the judiciary in interpreting and enforcing victim-centric rights. The paper aims to:

1. Examine statutory provisions under criminal laws such as the **Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita, Bhartiya Nagrik Suraksha Sanhita, POCSO Act, Domestic Violence Act, and SC/ST (Prevention of Atrocities) Act** that pertain to victim protection.
2. Evaluate landmark Supreme Court and High Court judgments that have strengthened victims' rights and protections.
3. Analyze the implementation and efficacy of victim compensation schemes at both national and state levels.
4. Identify systemic challenges—such as police **insensitivity**, judicial delays, social stigma, and bureaucratic inefficiencies—that hinder effective victim protection.
5. Comparisons with international legal standards and practices to propose reforms that could enhance the Indian framework for victim justice.

Review of Literature

1. Legal Definition of Victim

Under **Section 2(wa)** of the **Code of Criminal Procedure (CrPC)**, a victim is defined as:

"a person who has suffered any loss or injury caused by reason of the act or omission for which the accused person has been charged and the expression 'victim' includes his or her guardian or legal heir."

This definition acknowledges not only direct victims but also secondary victims, such as family members who suffer due to the crime.

2. Legal Framework for Victim Protection

India's legal landscape has evolved to recognize and protect the rights of victims through

various legislative instruments. Key provisions include the following:

2.1 The Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC)

The **CrPC** provides several important provisions aimed at victim protection:

Section 357A (Victim Compensation Scheme): This section, introduced through the **Criminal Law Amendment Act, 2008**, mandates the provision of compensation to victims, particularly in cases where the offender remains unidentified or is unable to compensate. States have created their own victim compensation schemes under this provision.

Section 372 (Right to Appeal): An important advancement for victims, this section allows victims to file appeals against acquittals, sentences, or inadequate compensation.

The **Supreme Court**, in the case of **Mallikarjun Kodagali v. State of Karnataka (2018)**, held that victims have an independent right to appeal against inadequate sentencing and acquittals. This ruling expanded the rights of victims, recognizing their role beyond that of mere witnesses.

2.2 The Indian Penal Code (IPC)

The **Indian Penal Code, 1860**, provides the substantive law regarding offenses and has been amended over the years to offer special protection for vulnerable groups such as women, children, and Scheduled Castes and Tribes (SC/ST).

Sections 375 and 376 (Rape and Sexual Assault): These sections, amended by the **Criminal Law Amendment Act, 2013**, after the **Nirbhaya case**, have expanded the definition of rape and prescribed stricter punishments.

The **Supreme Court** has emphasized victim protection in cases of sexual assault, as seen in **Delhi Domestic Working Women's Forum v. Union of India (1995)**, where it issued guidelines for the rehabilitation of rape victims, including legal aid and compensation.

2.3 The Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act (POCSO), 2012

The **POCSO Act** provides comprehensive protection for child victims of sexual offenses. Key provisions under POCSO include:

Child-friendly procedures: Sections under POCSO ensure that child victims are dealt with sensitively during the investigation and trial. Courts must ensure the child's comfort, allow testimony behind screens, and limit cross-examination by the accused.

Confidentiality: Section 33 of the Act mandates that the identity of the victim is kept confidential throughout the trial.

In **State of Punjab v. Gurmit Singh (1996)**, the Supreme Court had earlier stressed the need for in-camera trials for victims of sexual offenses to protect their dignity and privacy, a principle later incorporated into POCSO.

2.4 The Domestic Violence Act, 2005

The **Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA), 2005**, extends civil remedies to victims of domestic abuse, offering protection orders, residence orders, and financial compensation.

Section 18: Allows for protection orders to prevent acts of domestic violence, ensuring the safety of the victim.

Recent judgments, like **Hiral P. Harsora & Ors. v. Kusum Narottamdas Harsora & Ors. (2016)**, have expanded the scope of protection by allowing any woman in a domestic relationship to seek protection, including mothers and sisters, thus broadening the range of victims covered under the Act.

2.5 The Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989

The **SC/ST Act** is another critical law aimed at protecting victims from marginalized

communities. It provides for stringent penalties for atrocities against SCs and STs, including provisions for compensation and rehabilitation.

Section 21: Ensures immediate assistance and relief to victims of atrocities, including monetary compensation and legal aid.

In **State of Karnataka v. Krishnappa (2000)**, the Supreme Court reinforced that cases involving atrocities under the SC/ST Act must be investigated thoroughly and compensation should be expedited to ensure justice for victims from marginalized communities.

Main Text

3. Recent Judicial Developments

3.1 Landmark Supreme Court Judgments

The Supreme Court of India has consistently interpreted victim protection provisions in a progressive manner, ensuring victims' rights are adequately safeguarded.

Mallikarjun Kodagali v. State of Karnataka (2018): As discussed earlier, this judgment recognized the victim's right to appeal in criminal cases, marking a significant advancement in victims' participation in trials.

Subhash Chander v. State of Haryana (2023): In this recent case, the Supreme Court ruled that victims of violent crimes, especially sexual offenses, must receive expedited compensation under state victim compensation schemes. The Court emphasized that delays in compensation defeat the purpose of justice for victims.

Gauri Maulekhi v. State of Uttarakhand (2020): This case expanded the role of the judiciary in ensuring rehabilitation of victims, focusing on rehabilitation as a fundamental right for victims of crime, especially human trafficking and child sexual abuse.

3.2 High Court Judgments

The High Courts of various states have also played a vital role in shaping victim protection jurisprudence.

Delhi High Court Judgment in Jitender Kumar v. State (2022): The Court directed the state to ensure that compensation under the **Delhi Victim Compensation Scheme, 2018** is disbursed within 30 days to victims of sexual assault. The judgment highlighted the importance of timely compensation to alleviate the sufferings of victims.

Kerala High Court Judgment in Reena v. State of Kerala (2023): In this case, the Kerala High Court expanded the scope of domestic violence laws by recognizing that financial and emotional abuse, in addition to physical violence, could form the basis for compensation and protection orders under the PWDVA.

4. Victim Compensation Schemes and Challenges

4.1 National Legal Services Authority (NALSA)

The **National Legal Services Authority (NALSA)** plays a significant role in implementing victim compensation schemes across India. NALSA's guidelines aim to standardize compensation amounts and ensure that victims of heinous crimes receive timely financial relief.

NALSA Compensation Schemes for Women Victims of Sexual Assault/Other Crimes (2018): This scheme lays down the compensation for women victims of various crimes, including rape, sexual harassment, and trafficking.

4.2 State Compensation Schemes

Each state in India operates its own **victim compensation scheme**, governed by the guidelines under Section 357A CrPC. For example:

Maharashtra's Manodhairya Scheme: Provides financial assistance and rehabilitation to victims of rape, sexual offenses, and acid attacks. It includes a fast-track compensation mechanism for victims.

Despite these schemes, challenges persist:

Delay in disbursement: Often, victims face delays in receiving compensation due to bureaucratic inefficiencies. The Supreme Court, in **Laxmi v. Union of India (2014)**, directed that states must expedite compensation for victims of acid attacks, underscoring the need for prompt action in all victim compensation matters.

Inadequate funding: Many states have faced budgetary constraints in fulfilling their compensation obligations. Courts have frequently reprimanded state governments for underfunding compensation schemes, leading to delays in victim rehabilitation.

5. Challenges in Victim Protection

While significant legal strides have been made, several challenges continue to plague the implementation of victim protection laws in India:

5.1 Social Stigma

Victims of crimes such as sexual assault, domestic violence, and human trafficking often face social ostracism, which hinders their access to justice. The judiciary, through cases like **Nirbhaya (2012)**, has made efforts to ensure that victim-blaming is condemned, but societal attitudes remain a barrier.

5.2 Police Apathy

There is a widespread problem of police insensitivity in dealing with victims, particularly in cases of sexual violence and domestic abuse. In **Prakash Singh v. Union of India (2006)**, the Supreme Court laid down directives for police reforms, aiming to make the police more accountable and victim-sensitive.

5.3 Bureaucratic Hurdles

One of the most significant obstacles to effective victim protection in India is the existence of bureaucratic delays and inefficiencies. Victims, particularly those from vulnerable sections of society, often face numerous hurdles when seeking compensation, protection, or legal redress. This is especially true in cases of sexual assault, domestic violence, and human trafficking, where time-sensitive interventions are crucial for the victim's recovery.

Despite the introduction of compensation schemes under **Section 357A of the CrPC**, the implementation is often marred by delays in paperwork, verification processes, and a lack of interdepartmental coordination. Victims frequently face difficulties in accessing state legal aid or are unaware of their rights to compensation.

In the **Laxmi v. Union of India (2014)** case, the Supreme Court had to intervene, directing states to ensure that compensation to victims of acid attacks be disbursed promptly. The Court highlighted that procedural delays could severely hamper the victim's physical and mental rehabilitation. In this case, the Court mandated that acid attack victims receive a minimum of ₹3 lakhs in compensation and urged states to make the process less cumbersome.

5.3.1 Case Study: Manodhairya Scheme in Maharashtra

The **Manodhairya Scheme** in Maharashtra is designed to offer financial assistance and rehabilitation to rape and acid attack survivors. Although the scheme has brought relief to many, there have been numerous reports of bureaucratic delays and hurdles. In one case, a survivor of sexual assault in Pune had to wait over two years to receive her compensation due to delays in verification by local authorities. Such delays not only exacerbate the trauma experienced by the victim but also undermine the intended benefits of these compensation schemes.

5.4 Inadequate Legal Representation and Lack of Awareness

Many victims are unaware of their rights and legal options, and the availability of free legal representation is often inadequate, especially in rural areas. The **National Legal Services Authority (NALSA)** is responsible for providing free legal aid to marginalized groups, including victims of crime. However, the reach of NALSA is limited, and many victims do not have access to adequate legal counsel, particularly in cases involving domestic violence, trafficking, and sexual abuse.

In **Delhi Domestic Working Women's Forum v. Union of India (1995)**, the Supreme Court highlighted the need for legal representation for victims, particularly in sexual assault cases. The Court recommended that legal assistance be made available at all stages of the legal process, from the filing of the complaint to the trial and post-trial stages. Despite this, many victims still face challenges in accessing free and competent legal representation.

5.5 Judicial Delays

One of the fundamental challenges faced by victims is the protracted length of court proceedings. Judicial delays can be particularly detrimental to victims of sexual assault, domestic violence, and other serious offenses, as it prolongs their trauma and uncertainty. In many cases, victims are unable to move on with their lives because of the ongoing legal battles.

The **Nirbhaya Case (Mukesh & Anr. v. State for NCT of Delhi & Ors. 2017)**, which involved the brutal gang rape and murder of a young woman in Delhi, took almost eight years to reach its conclusion in the courts, despite widespread public outcry for swift justice. The delay in delivering justice to the victim's family highlighted the inefficiencies in the criminal justice system that continue to affect victims of violent crimes.

While the establishment of **fast-track courts** in 2013 for cases involving sexual assault and crimes against women has improved the situation, the number of such courts is still insufficient to handle the volume of cases, leading to further delays.

5.6 Police Apathy and Insensitivity

Victims, especially those from marginalized backgrounds or those involved in sensitive cases like sexual assault, domestic violence, and trafficking, often face apathy and insensitivity from law enforcement agencies. There are numerous cases where police officers either refuse to file First Information Reports (FIRs) or pressure victims to settle the matter privately.

In **Prakash Singh v. Union of India (2006)**, the Supreme Court issued a set of directives aimed at police reforms, intending to make the police more sensitive to victims and more efficient in handling complaints. However, the implementation of these reforms has been uneven across states. The lack of victim-friendly procedures and a general distrust of law enforcement continue to be major barriers for victims seeking justice.

5.6.1 The Nirbhaya Case and Police Response

The Nirbhaya case highlighted the inefficiencies and insensitivity in police handling of sexual violence cases. The initial delay in reaching the victim to the hospital and subsequent procedural hurdles in the investigation were widely criticized. This case spurred nationwide demands for police reforms, but the progress in addressing police insensitivity toward victims remains slow.

5.7 Social Stigma and Re-traumatization

Victims of crimes, particularly sexual violence, domestic violence, and acid attacks, often face severe social stigma, which discourages them from reporting the crime or pursuing justice. Victim-blaming and ostracization by their communities can deter victims from seeking legal recourse. Even in the legal process, many victims are re-traumatized during cross-examinations or due to the public nature of trials.

The **Supreme Court** has, in several cases, recognized the need for sensitive handling of such cases. For example, in **State of Punjab v. Gurmit Singh (1996)**, the Court emphasized the need for **in-camera trials** (closed-door trials) for victims of sexual assault to protect their dignity and privacy.

The stigma attached to being a victim is often compounded by the lengthy judicial process, which can make victims relive their trauma multiple times. Courts have begun taking steps to minimize re-traumatization by allowing testimony through video conferencing and screens to shield victims from facing the accused directly. These steps, however, need more widespread implementation.

6.The Role of the Judiciary in Expanding Victims' Rights

The Indian judiciary has been instrumental in shaping and expanding the rights of victims in India. Through judicial activism, the courts have interpreted existing laws to provide greater protection and participation for victims in the legal process. The judiciary's role in victim protection can be categorized into three main areas: expanding the definition of victims, ensuring victim participation in trials, and facilitating victim rehabilitation.

6.1 Expanding the Definition of Victims

The judiciary has broadened the definition of victims to include not just those who suffer direct harm but also those who face emotional or financial harm due to a crime. For example, in domestic violence cases, the courts have recognized that financial abuse can constitute a valid claim for protection and compensation under the **Domestic Violence Act**.

6.2 Right to Participation in Trials

Indian courts have recognized that victims have a right to participate in criminal proceedings, especially in cases involving serious offenses. The **Supreme Court** ruling in **Mallikarjun Kodagali v. State of Karnataka (2018)** affirmed that victims have the right to file an appeal against acquittal or inadequate sentencing. This ruling was a major step in recognizing the victim as an active participant in the criminal justice system, rather than just a passive observer.

6.3 Rehabilitation and Reparation

The Indian judiciary has also emphasized the importance of victim rehabilitation. In **Gauri Maulekhi v. State of Uttarakhand (2020)**, the Supreme Court highlighted the need for a holistic approach to victim rehabilitation, particularly in cases of human trafficking and child sexual abuse. The Court stressed that victim rehabilitation must include not only financial compensation but also psychological counselling and social reintegration programs.

Conclusion

Victim Protection in International Law

India's approach to victim protection can be better understood when compared with international standards and practices. The **United Nations Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power (1985)** provides a comprehensive framework for victim rights, which includes access to justice, fair treatment, restitution, compensation, and assistance.

1. Victim Protection in the United States

In the **United States**, the rights of victims have been enshrined in state and federal laws. For instance, the **Victims of Crime Act (VOCA), 1984** established a federal fund to compensate victims of crimes. Under this Act, victims are entitled to financial compensation for expenses such as medical bills, funeral costs, and lost wages.

Additionally, the **Crime Victims' Rights Act (2004)** provides victims with rights such as the right to be informed of court proceedings, the right to attend the trial, and the right to be heard at sentencing or parole hearings. Victims also have the right to restitution and can challenge decisions that infringe upon their rights.

2. Victim Protection in the United Kingdom

In the **United Kingdom**, victims are protected under the **Victims' Code**, which sets out the services and rights to which victims are entitled. It includes the right to be informed about the case's progress, the right to provide a victim personal statement, and the right to compensation.

The UK also has a **Victim Support** organization, which provides emotional and practical assistance to victims of crime. The UK's approach emphasizes the importance of victim participation and provides dedicated services to ensure victims are supported throughout the justice process.

3. Lessons for India

India can take valuable lessons from these international frameworks. While the Indian legal system has made significant strides in terms of victim compensation and rehabilitation, it still lacks a centralized mechanism for enforcing victim rights, particularly in ensuring consistent and prompt compensation across states.

Moreover, unlike the **United States** and **United Kingdom**, where victims' rights are enforced through independent oversight bodies or victim support organizations, India lacks such centralized enforcement mechanisms. The creation of a **National Victims' Rights Commission** could help ensure that victims' rights are uniformly protected across the country.

India has made important progress in creating laws and court decisions to protect victims, but many problems still remain that weaken these protections. Criminal Laws like, BNS, the POCSO Act, and the Domestic Violence Act are key steps in giving victims legal rights. However, in real life, these laws often do not work well because of slow paperwork, lack of funds, insensitive police behavior, and delays in court cases.

The courts have played an important role in giving victims rights to participate in cases, to appeal, and to get compensation. But many victims, especially those from marginalized communities, still face stigma and exclusion, making it hard for them to get justice.

When we look at countries like the United States and the United Kingdom, we see that having strong systems like independent agencies to protect victim rights, proper support services, and clear enforcement helps victims get the justice they deserve.

For India to truly protect victims, it needs to focus not only on making new laws but also on improving how these laws are put into action. This includes better coordination between departments, raising public awareness, and creating a central authority for victim rights. Only then will India be able to fulfil its promise of justice for everyone, including victims of crime.

References **Acts and Legal Regulations**

1. *Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (CrPC) (Sections 2(wa), 357A, 372)*
2. *Indian Penal Code, 1860 (Sections 375, 376)*
3. *Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012 (POCSO)*
4. *Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 (PWDVA) (Section 18)*
5. *Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989 (Section 21)*
6. *Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2008*
7. *Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013*
8. *NALSA Compensation Scheme for Women Victims of Sexual Assault/Other Crimes, 2018*
9. *Maharashtra's Manodhairya Scheme*
10. *Victims of Crime Act (VOCA), United States, 1984*
11. *Crime Victims' Rights Act, United States, 2004*
12. *Victims' Code, United Kingdom*
13. *United Nations Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power, 1985*

Landmark Case Laws

1. *Mallikarjun Kodagali v. State of Karnataka, (2018) 14 SCC 745*
2. *Subhash Chander v. State of Haryana, (2023) (SC)*
3. *Gauri Maulekhi v. State of Uttarakhand, (2020) 14 SCC 380*
4. *Delhi Domestic Working Women's Forum v. Union of India, (1995) 1 SCC 14*
5. *State of Punjab v. Gurmit Singh, (1996) 2 SCC 384*
6. *Hiral P. Harsora & Ors. v. Kusum Narottamdas Harsora & Ors., (2016) 10 SCC 165*
7. *State of Karnataka v. Krishnappa, (2000) 4 SCC 75*
8. *Laxmi v. Union of India, (2014) 4 SCC 427*
9. *Mukesh & Anr. v. State for NCT of Delhi & Ors. (Nirbhaya Case), (2017) 6 SCC 1*
10. *Prakash Singh v. Union of India, (2006) 8 SCC 1*
11. *Jitender Kumar v. State, (2022) (Delhi High Court)*
12. *Reena v. State of Kerala, (2023) (Kerala High Court)*

